

STRUCTURES AND PROPERTIES OF Fe₃O₄-CARBON MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES NANOFIBRES

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ABSTRACT

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-Fe₃O₄ composite nanofibres were fabricated by the co-electrospinning process. These nanofibres were carbonized to obtain tailored electromagnetic properties. Four-probe and SQUID measurements showed tailorable electromagnetic properties were achieved by controlling nanoparticles contents and carbonization temperature. Higher saturation magnetization of about 16 emu/g was obtained for sample with higher Fe₃O₄ content at higher carbonization temperature (900°C). The electrical conductivity was also increased with increasing the Fe₃O₄ content

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanofibres have attracted great interest in the last few decades due to their widespread applications as gas sensors ^[1], hydrogen storage media ^[2], electromagnetic interference shielding ^[3], catalysts and catalytic supports ^[4], field-emission microelectronic devices ^[5], etc. Among different methods of synthesizing carbon nanofibres, electrospinning is one of the easiest and cost-effective techniques.

Due to its typical magnetic and electrical properties, magnetite (Fe₃O₄) is one of the preferred and best characterized filler material, which is used in combination with polymers, e.g. for recording media, in medical applications, in building industry for damping applications and for absorption of radiation ^[6]. In the last few decades, the C/magnetic nanoparticle composites have been promising materials in different range of applications in numerous fields of applications. For example, Reneker and Hou ^[7] have prepared a catalyst for Carbon nanotube growth by heat treating the PAN/iron salt by reducing the iron salt into the iron nanoparticles in an appropriate atmosphere. Wang et al. ^[8] synthesized the C/Fe₃O₄ electrospun nanofibre composite and investigated their application as promising anode materials for high performance lithium-ion batteries.

In the present work, the Carbon nanofibre/Fe₃O₄ nanofibre composite was prepared using electrospinning and subsequent pyrolysis with the electromagnetic nanofibre composite. Magnetite nanoparticles was use as magnetic fillers of the PAN due to it excellent magnetic properties. On the other hand, PAN was selected as a polymer matrix of this composite, since it is an electrospinnable polymer with the ability to be pyrolyzed at high temperatures to make carbon nanofibres. The main objective of the present study is to the feasibility of preparing composite electromagnetic nanofibres and characterizes their structure and properties.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

1, 5, 10 wt% Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (~20-30nm) were dispersed in 10% PAN/DMF (Dimethylformamide) solution using PVP as surfactant. The prepared solution was spun into composite nanofibre using the electrospinning process. These nanofibres were stabilized at 250°C under O₂ for two hours and subsequently carbonized at 700°C and

900°C under N₂ for one hour. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM), X-ray Diffractometry (XRD), Four-point probe and Superconducting Quantum Interference Devices (SQUID) were used for characterization of the composite nanofibre assemblies.

Figure 1. Carbonization process.

3. RESULTS

3-1. Microstructural analysis

Figure 2 shows the Scanning Electron Microscopy images of pure Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) electrospun nanofibres before and after carbonization. According to these images, the fibre diameter decreases after pyrolysis at both 700°C and 900°C from 370 nm to 270 nm for pure nanofibres carbonized at 700°C and from 390 nm to 265 nm for pure nanofibres carbonized at 900°C.

Figure 2. SEM image of pure PAN before and after carbonization at 700 and 900C.

Figure 3 shows the SEM images of electrospun nanofibre composite containing 10%Fe₃O₄ in 10% PAN. Fibre diameter decreases after carbonization as expected from 570 nm to 410 nm after carbonization at 700°C and from 570 nm to 350 nm after carbonization at 900°C. In addition, comparing the fibre diameter from pure PAN to composite Fe₃O₄/PAN nanofibre, the fibre diameter is totally increasing by incorporation the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles inside the PAN nanofibres.

Figure 3. SEM image of Electrospun 10%Fe₃O₄/PAN nanofibre before and after carbonization at 700°C and 900°C.

Table 1 Summary of fibre diameter before and after carbonization:

Sample	Non-carbonized nanofibre	Carbonized at 700°C	Carbonized at 900°C
Pure PAN nanofibre	370 nm	270 nm	-
	390 nm	-	265 nm
10% Fe ₃ O ₄ /PAN nanofibre	570 nm	410 nm	350 nm

Figure 4 shows the Transmission Electron Microscopy images of Electrospun 10%Fe₃O₄/PAN nanofibre before and after carbonization at 700°C and 900°C. The pictures show a relatively good dispersion of nanoparticles inside the nanofibres. Moreover, the particles size increases after carbonizing the composite nanofibres at both 700 and 900C. Especially, higher pyrolysis temperature results in larger particle size.

Figure 4. TEM images of 10%Fe₃O₄/PAN electrospun nanofibre before and after carbonization at 700°C and 900°C

Figure 5 shows the XRD spectra of magnetite nanoparticles, carbonized pure PAN nanofibre and 1, 5 and 10%Fe₃O₄/PAN nanofibres carbonized at 900°C. Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles have been used as fillers in making the composite. During the pyrolysis process (stabilization at 250°C under the oxygen atmosphere and carbonization at 900°C under the nitrogen atmosphere), XRD shows the magnetite and carbon peaks which have been determined in figure 5.

Figure 5. X-ray diffraction of electrospun nanofibre composites after carbonization at 900°C.

3-2. Physical properties

3-2-1. Electrical conductivity

Electrical conductivity measurements were performed using four-point probe method and the results have been summarized in Table 2. According to the results, the electrical conductivity rises with increasing the pyrolysis temperature from 700°C to 900°C. For example, for composite nanofibres of 10%Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, the conductivity can increase from 1.49 S/cm up to 9.86 S/cm which has been reported by Wang et al. [9] as well. In addition to the effect of the carbonization temperature in electrical conductivity, magnetic nanoparticles have an efficient effect on electrical conductivity.

In the magnetite network because of the contact between the magnetite elements or very small gaps among them the migration of charge carriers is possible from one magnetite particle to another being done by hopping or tunnelling. Since the tunnelling or hopping probability of an electron is always an inverse exponential function of the width of the gap, as the concentration of magnetite is increased, the gap between magnetite aggregates decreases and the resistivity decreases [10,11]. Therefore, according to our results, magnetite can contribute to the migration of charge carriers and rising the electrical conductivity.

Table 2 Electrical conductivity of Fe₃O₄/PAN composite nanofibres carbonized at 700°C and 900°C:

Sample Code	carbonized at 700°C	carbonized at 900°C
1%Fe ₃ O ₄	0.032 S/cm	3.89 S/cm
5%Fe ₃ O ₄	0.304 S/cm	6.34 S/cm
10%Fe ₃ O ₄	1.49 S/cm	9.86 S/cm
Pure PAN	0.03	3.86

3-2-2. Magnetic properties

Figure 6 shows the M-H curve of 5 and 10% Fe₃O₄ non-carbonized electrospun nanofibres and composite electrospun nanofibres carbonized at 700°C and 900°C.

Figure 6. M-H curve of 5 and 10% Fe₃O₄ non-carbonized electrospun nanofibres and composite electrospun nanofibres carbonized at 700°C and 900°C.

According to the M-H curves shown in figure 6, the saturation magnetization of the carbonized composite nanofibres increases with increase in the pyrolysis temperature and from TEM images it can be attributed to the larger particles size at higher carbonization temperatures which has been reported in [12] that saturation magnetization is a function of average crystallite size of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles mean while the coercivity increases which is being related to the coercivity dependence of the size of nanoparticles.

4. CONCLUSION

Fe₃O₄-polymer composite nanofibres have been successfully fabricated, demonstrating the capability of translating electromagnetic properties of the nanoparticles to the fibrous structure. It was found that the saturation magnetization increases with increasing Fe₃O₄ content and the pyrolysis temperature up to 16 emu/g. However, the coercivity also increases with increasing the temperature which can be attributed to the fact that particles diffuse into each other at higher temperatures and the size increases which is in good agreement with the TEM pictures. Besides, the highest electrical conductivity of about 9.86 S/cm was obtained for higher Fe₃O₄ content and higher pyrolysis temperature 900°C. Carbonization of the composite nanofibres provided additional processing route to optimize the conductivity and saturation magnetization of the composite nanofibres. This electromagnetic composite nanofibre has the potential for a wide range of applications

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Jang, J. Bae, Sens. Actuators B 122 (2007) 7–13.

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- [2] H.W. Zhu, X.S. Li, L.J. Ci, C.L. Xu, D.H. Wu, Z.Q. Mao, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 78 (2003) 670–675.
- [3] Sh. Yang, K. Lozano, A. Lomeli, H. D. Foltz, R. Jones, *Composites: Part A* 36 (2005) 691–697.
- [4] M. Endo, Y.A. Kim, M. Ezaka, K. Osada, T. Yanagisawa, T. Hayashi, M. Terrones, M.S. Dresselhaus, *Nanoletters* 3 (2003) 723–727.
- [5] K.B.K. Teo, M. Chhowalla, G.A.J. Amareatunga, W.I. Milne, G. Pirio, P. Legagneux, F. Wyczisk, D. Pribat, D.G. Hasko, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 80 (2002) 2011–2013.
- [6] B. Weidenfeller, M. Höfer, F. Schilling, *Composites: Part A* 33 (2002) 1041–1053.
- [7] H. Hou, D.H. Reneker, *Adv. Mater.*, 2004, 16, 69–73.
- [8] L. Wang, Y. Yu, P.C. Chen, D.W. Zhang, C.H. Chen, *Journal of Power Sources* 183 (2008) 717–723.
- [9] Y. Wang, J. J. Santiago-Aviles, R. Furlan, and I. Ramos, *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON NANOTECHNOLOGY*, VOL. 2, NO. 1, MARCH 2003.
- [10] M. Narkis, A. Vaxman, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 29 (1984) 1639–1652.
- [11] Muhammad Yasar Razzaq, Mathias Anhalt, Lars Frommann, Bernd Weidenfeller, *Materials Science and Engineering A* 444 (2007) 227–235.
- [12] Ch. Lin, Y. Chu, Sh. Wang, *Materials Letters* 60 (2006) 447–450.